

Embedding-Based Face Recognition Using FaceNet512: A Deployment-Oriented Technical Study

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Abstract

This work examines the practical deployment of an embedding-based face recognition and authentication system built using pretrained deep learning models. The system combines RetinaFace for face detection and FaceNet512 for facial embedding generation through the DeepFace framework. Identity verification is carried out by comparing embeddings using cosine similarity with a fixed threshold value of 0.7.

The full pipeline was implemented as a RESTful API using FastAPI so that registration and authentication can be performed through simple API requests. Evaluation was conducted using a small controlled identity set consisting of 10 registered individuals. For each identity, repeated authentication trials were performed under indoor lighting conditions. Additional tests were also carried out using printed and digital photographs to observe whether non-live inputs would be incorrectly accepted.

The current implementation produced an average authentication time of approximately 11 seconds per request when executed on CPU-only hardware. No false acceptance was observed during photograph-based attempts. The results indicate that while the system functions reliably at small scale, feature extraction and face detection remain the dominant computational bottlenecks.

Keywords: Face Recognition, FaceNet512, RetinaFace, Authentication, FastAPI, Deployment Study

1 Introduction

Face recognition has become a widely used biometric authentication approach because it allows identity verification without physical contact and can be integrated easily into software systems. Recent face recognition pipelines rely on pretrained deep learning models that convert facial images into fixed-length embeddings, where similar identities remain close in feature space.

Although such models provide strong recognition capability, practical deployment introduces challenges when inference must be performed under limited hardware resources. In many lightweight systems, latency becomes a critical concern even when recognition quality remains acceptable.

This work does not attempt to introduce a new recognition model. Instead, it focuses on studying how an existing embedding-based pipeline behaves when deployed as an authentication system.

The main contributions of this study are:

- Design of a face authentication pipeline using RetinaFace and FaceNet512.

- Deployment of the complete system using FastAPI.
- Evaluation of authentication latency under CPU-only execution.
- Simple presentation attack testing using printed and digital photographs.

2 Related Work

Modern face recognition systems largely depend on deep metric learning. FaceNet introduced the use of triplet loss to map facial images into an embedding space where identities can be separated effectively [1]. ArcFace later improved this idea by introducing angular margin constraints to increase discriminative power [2]. RetinaFace demonstrated strong face detection capability under varied visual conditions by using dense landmark supervision [3].

Unlike studies that mainly focus on improving recognition accuracy, the present work examines deployment-related behavior such as latency and storage requirements.

3 Methodology

The system operates in two stages: registration and authentication.

During registration, an input facial image is first processed using RetinaFace to detect the face region. The detected face is then passed through FaceNet512 using the DeepFace framework [4] to generate a 512-dimensional embedding. This embedding is stored together with the identity label.

During authentication, the same preprocessing steps are applied to a query image. Cosine similarity is computed between the query embedding and all stored embeddings. If the highest similarity exceeds 0.7, authentication is accepted.

Figure 1: Overview of the registration and authentication flow used in the system

4 Experimental Setup

The implementation was carried out in Python and exposed through FastAPI as a RESTful service.

A controlled identity set of 10 individuals was used for testing. Each registered identity underwent at least five authentication attempts under indoor lighting conditions.

To observe behavior against simple presentation attacks, additional attempts were made using printed photographs and digital photographs of registered users. In these tests, no false acceptance was observed.

All experiments were executed on an Intel Core i5 CPU environment without GPU acceleration.

5 Evaluation Metrics

5.1 Authentication Latency

Authentication latency represents the total time required for face detection, embedding generation, and identity verification.

5.2 Memory Footprint per Identity

Memory footprint refers to storage required for one embedding vector together with its associated identity label.

6 Results

A total of 50 authentication trials were performed.

Table 1: System-level evaluation metrics

Metric	Observed Value
Embedding Dimension	512
Authentication Threshold	0.7
Average Authentication Latency	11 seconds
Approximate Storage per Identity	2 KB

Table 2: Authentication evaluation summary

Parameter	Value
Registered identities	10
Trials per identity	5 minimum
Total trials	50
Photo-based attack test	Printed / digital photographs
False acceptance observed	0

Table 3: Approximate latency contribution by stage

Pipeline Stage	Time Contribution
Face Detection	4.5 seconds
Embedding Extraction	5.0 seconds
Similarity Search	1.5 seconds

The results show that most of the total processing time is spent in face detection and embedding extraction.

7 Discussion

The observed latency suggests that repeated execution of pretrained deep models becomes the main limitation when running on CPU-only hardware.

Although the evaluation scale is small, repeated trials showed stable authentication behavior under controlled conditions. The current setup remains limited by sample size and controlled image acquisition.

8 Conclusion

This study examined the deployment behavior of a face authentication pipeline built using FaceNet512 and RetinaFace.

The system performed reliably for a small number of identities, but computational latency remains the major limitation for scaling.

Future work can focus on approximate nearest-neighbor retrieval, embedding compression, and evaluation on larger identity sets.

References

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